

IN THE PROCESS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE LESSONS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS SPIRITUAL AND ETHICAL PRINCIPLES OF MODERN SOCIETY AND VALUES

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Abstract: *In this scientific article, the moral and ethical principles of modern society in technical higher education institutions and values are revealed. A person who entered the common cultural space of higher education, a student, the whole nation, is the language of inter-ethnic communication and should have different tools.*

Key words: *spiritual and moral principles, values, student, language of communication, approach, education.*

Today, spiritual and moral education needs a theoretical understanding of its methodological foundations and the development of a holistic approach to them. A new stage of the development of the society has begun due to the change in the mentality of the society and the personality, the change in the values of the young generation. Only those who cannot eat the need to educate a creative, spiritually rich, high-spirited person is becoming more and more acute. Spiritual and moral development of students is the most important aspect of socialization of a person in the conditions of rapid development of society, a factor of gradual and conscious participation in various spheres of social activity and community life.

It is clear that in order to become a full participant in the global cultural process, modern higher education students must master the spiritual and moral values that have accumulated over the centuries in human history. A person entering a cultural space and the whole nation should have various means of inter-ethnic

communication. That's it from this point of view, knowing at least one foreign language plays a big role. Language is a storehouse of ethno-culture, it contains the entire cognitive experience of people, its moral-ethical, social - covers cultural, artistic and aesthetic, educational ideals. Teaching foreign languages to modern higher education students unique pedagogical process of spiritual, moral, ideological, political, aesthetic, labor education of the young generation includes potential.

The purpose of the work is to theoretically justify and test the pedagogical conditions for the implementation of spiritual and moral education of schoolchildren in French language classes. In studying the problem, he set the following tasks in accordance with the goal, research object and subject:

1. Study of pedagogical literature on spiritual and moral education of students.
2. Choosing a methodological basis for studying the moral qualities of students in the process of teaching a foreign language.
3. The most effective methods of moral education of students used by foreign language teachers and identify methods.

Spiritual and moral education of students is successfully carried out:

- in the implementation of educational opportunities according to the content of the educational material in the lesson;
- when the teacher uses methods and tools that help to form moral knowledge and skills.

The logic of the research is the theoretical understanding of the problem, methodological approaches to its solution; collecting empirical material, analyzing and summarizing the pedagogical experience of spiritual and moral education of schoolchildren using a foreign language.

Recently, it had an impact on the change of all aspects of young people's lives in the spiritual and moral sphere.

The need to establish a spiritually oriented paradigm of education, the effectiveness of solving the problems of spirituality is related to the value-semantic situation in the new Uzbekistan.

In conclusion, we say that spirituality is a quality characteristic of a person's mind and self-awareness, and it reflects the integrity and harmony of his inner world, the ability to go beyond his limits and harmonize his relations with the world around him. It is with a breadth and depth of educational, cultural needs and interests rather, it refers to the constant and unceasing work of the soul, to understand the world and oneself in this world, to strive for self-improvement, to change one's inner space. the world, to expand one's consciousness. It is also is a unique emotional structure of a person, it is in the subtle movements of the soul, everything that surrounds a person in high perception, in the ability to have a high spiritual state and to create subtle spiritual connections between people appears in the installation. sensitive attitude towards a person, about his spiritual growth and well-being to grieve.

The list of used literature

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